

Supplementary material – Figure 1 - 1A, 1B and 1C

Network-based approach to understand gene-biological processes affecting economic important traits of Nellore cattle

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Figure 1A: Bias analysis and quality in all studies included in the systematic review.

Quality criteria	Afonso et al., 2019 [11]	Alexandre et al., 2019 [12]	Berton et al., 2016 [6]	Cesar et al., 2015 [7]	Cesar et al., 2016 [25]	Diniz et al., 2016 [26]	Fausto et al., 2019 [20]	Fonseca et al., 2017 [27]	Fonseca et al., 2020 [28]	Gonçalves et al., 2018 [29]	Muniz et al., 2020 [30]	Olivieri et al., 2020 [31]	Santos-Silva et al., 2019 [32]	Santos-Silva et al., 2020 [33]	Silva-Vignato et al., 2017 [34]	Tizioto et al., 2015 [35]	Tizioto et al., 2016 [36]
Title																	
Accurate and concise description of the content of the article	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Summary of the background, objectives, methods, main findings and conclusions	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Sufficient scientific background	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Rational explanation of the experimental approach	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Clear primary and secondary objectives	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Ethical statement of animals																	
Ethical review permissions, licenses and official guidelines for use of animals	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Study design																	
Number of animals per group	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Information on whether the experiment was performed as a blind controlled study	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No

√, *Criteria completed. No, criteria not completed.*

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<i>Experimental animals</i>																	
Information regarding animal species	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Strain of the animals	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Sex of the animals	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	No	√	√
Weight range of the animals	No	√	√	√	√	No	√	No	No	No	No	√	No	No	No	No	No
Age of the animals	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Information related to previous procedures performed on the animals	√	√	No	√	√	No	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
<i>Housing and husbandry</i>																	
Welfare-related assessments before, during, or after the experiment	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
<i>Sample size</i>																	
Number of animals used in each experiment and group	√	√	No	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Explanation regarding number of animals and sample size calculation	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No

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<i>Allocating animals to groups</i>																	
Full details of how animals were allocated to groups	√	No	No	No	No	√	√	√	No	No	No	√	√	√	√	√	√
Order of animals inoculated and/or evaluated	No	No	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	No	√	√
<i>Experimental outcomes</i>																	
Clear experimental outcomes assessed	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
<i>Statistical methods</i>																	
Statistical methods used for each analysis	√	√	√	No	No	√	√	√	√	√	√	No	√	√	√	√	√
Specification of the unit of analysis for each dataset	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Methods used to assess adequacy of the statistical approach	No	√	√	No	No	No	√	No	No	No	√	No	No	No	No	√	No
Results																	
Baseline data	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Description of health status of animals	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√

√, *Criteria completed. No, criteria not completed.*

Figure 1A: (continuation): Bias analysis and quality in all studies included in the systematic review.

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Numbers analyzed																	
Number of animals in each group included in each analysis	√	√	No	√	No	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Data not included in the analysis (explanation of exclusion)	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Outcomes and estimation																	
Gene information	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Adverse events																	
Information regarding mortality	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Modifications to the protocols to reduce adverse events	√	√	No	No	No	No	√	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Discussion																	
Interpretation/scientific implications																	
Interpretation of the results, consider objectives, hypotheses, current theory	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Comments on limitations (bias, limitations of the model, imprecision of results)	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No

√, *Criteria completed. No, criteria not completed.*

Figure 1A: (continuation): Bias analysis and quality in all studies included in the systematic review.

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Quality criteria																	
<i>Generalizability/translation</i>																	
Comments on how the findings are likely to translate to other species	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
<i>Funding</i>																	
List of funding sources and the role of the funder(s) in the study	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Quality of publication																	
<i>Impact factor</i>																	
Periodic with Journal Citation Reports (JCR) for impact factor	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Criteria completed (n)	25	26	23	24	23	24	28	25	24	24	25	25	25	25	23	26	25
Criteria completed (%)	71	74	65	68	65	68	80	71	68	68	71	71	71	71	65	74	71

√, *Criteria completed. No, criteria not completed.*

Figure 1B: Biological Processes (GO terms) and pathways found to genes differentially expressed related meat traits of Nellore bulls. The bars represent the number of genes associated with the terms. The percentage of genes per term is shown as bar label.

Figure 1B: (continuation): Biological Processes (GO terms) and pathways found to genes differentially expressed related meat traits of Nellore bulls. The bars represent the number of genes associated with the terms. The percentage of genes per term is shown as bar label.

Figure 1B:

(continuation):

Biological Processes (GO terms) and pathways found to genes differentially expressed related meat traits of Nellore bulls. The bars represent the number of genes associated with the terms. The percentage of genes per term is shown as bar label.

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Figure 1B: (*continuation*): Biological Processes (GO terms) and pathways found to genes differentially expressed related meat traits of Nellore bulls. The bars represent the number of genes associated with the terms. The percentage of genes per term is shown as bar label.

Figure 1C: Overview chart with functional groups found to genes differentially expressed related meat traits of Nellore bulls

